

SOLVING SYSTEMS OF FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS BY HOMOTOPY-PERTURBATION METHOD

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Annotation. In this Letter, approximate analytical solutions of systems of Fractional Differential Equations (FDEs) are derived by the Homotopy-Perturbation Method (HPM). The fractional derivatives are described in the Caputo sense. The solutions are obtained in the form of rapidly convergent infinite series with easily computable terms. Numerical results reveal that HPM is very effective and simple for obtaining approximate solutions of nonlinear systems of FDEs.

Keywords. Homotopy-perturbation method; Fractional differential equations; Caputo fractional derivative

Аннотация. В этом письме приближенные аналитические решения систем дробных дифференциальных уравнений (ДДУ) выводятся с помощью метода гомотопии-возмущения (МГВ). Дробные производные описываются в смысле Капуто. Решения получаются в виде быстро сходящихся бесконечных рядов с легко вычисляемыми членами. Численные результаты показывают, что МГВ очень эффективен и прост для получения приближенных решений нелинейных систем ДДУ.

Ключевые слова. Метод гомотопии-возмущения; Дробные дифференциальные уравнения; Дробная производная Капуто.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar (KDT) tizimlarining taxminiy analitik yechimlari Gomotopiya-Perturbatsiya(tartibsizlik) Usuli (GPU) yordamida olingan. Kasr hosilalari Kaputo ma'nosida tasvirlangan. Yechimlar oson hisoblab chiqiladigan atamalar bilan tez yaqinlashuvchi cheksiz qatorlar shaklida olinadi. Raqamli natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, GPU KDT ning chiziqli bo'lmagan tizimlarining taxminiy echimlarini olish uchun juda samarali va oddiy.

Kalit so'zlar. Gomotopiya-Perturbatsiya Usuli; Kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar; Kaputo kasr hosilasi.

In the last decades, fractional calculus has found diverse applications in various scientific and technological fields [1,2], such as thermal engineering, acoustics, electromagnetism, control, robotics, viscoelasticity, diffusion, edge detection, turbulence, signal processing and many other physical processes. Fractional Differential Equations (FDEs) have also been applied in modelling many physical and engineering problems.

Finding accurate and efficient methods for solving FDEs has been an active research undertaking. Exact solutions of most of the FDEs cannot be found easily, thus analytical and numerical methods must be used. The Adomian Decomposition Method (ADM) was shown to be applicable to linear and nonlinear FDEs [3,4,5]. However, one of the disadvantages of ADM is the inherent difficulty in calculating the Adomian polynomials. Yet another promising analytic technique for nonlinear problems is called the homotopy-perturbation method (HPM). The HPM, a coupling of the traditional perturbation method and homotopy in topology, deforms continuously a difficult problem to a simple problem which is easily solved. The HPM does not require a small

parameter in an equation and the perturbation equation can be easily constructed by a homotopy in topology.

Many real-life applications are modelled by *systems* of FDEs which can be written in the form:

$$D^{\alpha_1} y_1(t) = f_1(t, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n), \quad (1)$$

$$D^{\alpha_1} y_2(t) = f_2(t, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n), \quad (2)$$

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$$D^{\alpha_n} y_n(t) = f_n(t, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n), \quad (3)$$

subject to the following initial conditions:

$$y_k(0) = c_k, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (4)$$

where D^{α_i} is the fractional derivative of y_i of order α_i ($0 < \alpha_i \leq 1$) and f_i are arbitrary linear or nonlinear functions.

In this Letter, we are interested in extending the applicability of HPM to systems of FDEs (1)–(3). To demonstrate the effectiveness of the HPM algorithm, several numerical experiments of linear and nonlinear systems of FDEs shall be presented.

Definition 1. Areal function $h(t), t > 0$, is said to be in the space $C_\mu, \mu \in R$, if there exists a real number $p > \mu$, such that $h(t) = t^p h_1(t)$, where $h_1(t) \in C(0, \infty)$, and it is said to be in the space C_μ^n if and only if $h^{(n)} \in C_\mu, n \in N$.

Definition 2. The Riemann–Liouville fractional integral operator (I^α) of order $\alpha \geq 0$, of a function $h \in C_\mu, \mu \geq -1$, is defined as

$$I^\alpha h(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} h(\tau) d\tau \quad (\alpha > 0), \quad (5)$$

$$I^0 h(t) = h(t),$$

where $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the well-known gamma function.

Some of the properties of the operator (I^α), which we will need here, are as follows: For $h \in C_\mu, \mu \geq -1, \alpha, \beta \geq 0$ and $n \geq -1$:

1. $I^\alpha I^\beta h(t) = I^{\alpha+\beta} h(t)$,
2. $I^\alpha I^\beta h(t) = I^\beta I^\alpha h(t)$,
3. $I^\alpha t^n = \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha+n+1)} t^{\alpha+n}$.

Definition 3. The fractional derivative (D^α) of $h(t)$ in the Caputo sense is defined as

$$D^\alpha h(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{n-\alpha-1} h^{(n)}(\tau) d\tau, \quad (6)$$

for $n-1 < \alpha \leq n, n \in N, t > 0, h \in C_{-1}^n$.

In view of the HPM [6,7], we construct the following homotopy:

$$D^{\alpha_i} y_i(t) = p f_i(t, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n), \quad (7)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and p is an embedding parameter which changes from zero to unity. If $p = 0$, Eq.(7) becomes the linear equation

$$D^{\alpha_i} y_i = 0,$$

and when $p = 1$, the homotopy (7) turns out to be the original system given in (1)-(3). Using the parameter p , we expand the solution of the system (1)-(3) in the following form:

$$y_i(t) = y_{i0} + py_{i1} + p^2 y_{i2} + p^3 y_{i3} + \dots \quad (8)$$

Substituting (8) into (7) and collecting the terms with the same powers of p , we obtain a series of linear equations of the form

$$p^0 : D^{\alpha_i} y_{i0} = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$p^1 : D^{\alpha_i} y_{i1} = f_{i1}(t, y_{10}, y_{20}, \dots, y_{n0}), \quad (10)$$

$$p^2 : D^{\alpha_i} y_{i2} = f_{i2}(t, y_{10}, y_{20}, \dots, y_{n0}, y_{11}, y_{21}, \dots, y_{n1}), \quad (11)$$

$$p^3 : D^{\alpha_i} y_{i3} = f_{i3}(t, y_{10}, y_{20}, \dots, y_{n0}, y_{11}, y_{21}, \dots, y_{n1}, y_{12}, y_{22}, \dots, y_{n2}), \quad (12)$$

etc., where the functions f_{i1}, f_{i2}, \dots , satisfy the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{i0}(t, y_{10} + py_{11} + p^2 y_{12} + \dots, \dots, y_{n0} + py_{n1} + p^2 y_{n2} + \dots) = \\ = f_{i1}(t, y_{10}, y_{20}, \dots, y_{n0}) + pf_{i2}(t, y_{10}, y_{20}, \dots, y_{n0}, y_{11}, y_{21}, \dots, y_{n1}) + \\ + p^2 f_{i3}(t, y_{10}, y_{20}, \dots, y_{n0}, y_{11}, y_{21}, \dots, y_{n1}, y_{12}, y_{22}, \dots, y_{n2}) + \dots \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious that these linear equations can be easily solved by applying the operator I^{α_i} , i.e., the inverse of the operator D^{α_i} , which is defined by (5). Hence, the components y_{ik} ($k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) of the HPM solution can be determined. That is, by setting $p = 1$ in (8) we can entirely determine the

HPM series solutions, $y_i(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} y_{ik}(t)$.

Example. Now let us consider the following nonlinear system of FDEs:

$$D^{\alpha} x(t) = zy, \quad (13)$$

$$D^{\beta} y(t) = xz, \quad (14)$$

$$D^{\gamma} z(t) = xy, \quad (15)$$

where $0 < \alpha, \beta, \gamma \leq 1$ and the initial conditions are as follows:

$$x(0) = 1, \quad y(0) = 1, \quad z(0) = 1. \quad (16)$$

According to (7) we construct the following homotopy:

$$D^{\alpha} x(t) = p(zy),$$

$$D^{\beta} y(t) = p(xz),$$

$$D^{\gamma} z(t) = p(xy),$$

substituting (8) into (7) and equating the terms with the same powers of p , the linear equations (9)–(12) for system (13)–(15) can be reduced to the following three sets of linear equations:

p^0	$D^{\alpha} x_0 = 0$	$D^{\beta} y_0 = 0$	$D^{\gamma} z_0 = 0$
p^1	$D^{\alpha} x_1 = z_0 y_0$	$D^{\beta} y_1 = z_0 x_0$	$D^{\gamma} z_1 = x_0 y_0$
p^2	$D^{\alpha} x_2 = z_0 y_1 + z_1 y_0$	$D^{\beta} y_2 = z_0 x_1 + z_1 x_0$	$D^{\gamma} z_2 = x_0 y_1 + x_1 y_0$

p^3	$D^\alpha x_3 = z_0 y_2 + z_1 y_1 + z_2 y_0$	$D^\beta y_3 = z_0 x_2 + z_1 x_1 + z_2 x_0$	$D^\gamma z_3 = x_0 y_2 + x_1 y_1 + x_2 y_0$
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Consequently, by applying the operators I^α , I^β and I^γ to the above sets of linear equations, the first few terms of the HPM series solution for the system (13)–(15) are obtained as follows:

$$x_0 = x(0) = 1,$$

$$x_1 = \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)},$$

$$x_2 = \frac{t^{\beta+\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + 1)} + \frac{t^{\gamma+\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha + \gamma + 1)},$$

$$x_3 = \frac{t^{\beta+2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha + \beta + 1)} + \frac{2t^{\beta+\alpha+\gamma}}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \gamma + 1)} + \frac{\Gamma(\gamma + \beta + 1)t^{\beta+\alpha+\gamma}}{\Gamma(\gamma + 1)\Gamma(\beta + 1)\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \gamma + 1)} + \frac{t^{\gamma+2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha + \gamma + 1)},$$

$$y_0 = y(0) = 1,$$

$$y_1 = \frac{t^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta + 1)},$$

$$y_2 = \frac{t^{\beta+\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + 1)} + \frac{t^{\gamma+\beta}}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + 1)},$$

$$y_3 = \frac{t^{2\beta+\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 2\beta + 1)} + \frac{2t^{\beta+\alpha+\gamma}}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \gamma + 1)} + \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \gamma + 1)t^{\beta+\alpha+\gamma}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)\Gamma(\gamma + 1)\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \gamma + 1)} + \frac{t^{\gamma+2\beta}}{\Gamma(2\beta + \gamma + 1)},$$

$$z_0 = z(0) = 1,$$

$$z_1 = \frac{t^\gamma}{\Gamma(\gamma + 1)},$$

$$z_2 = \frac{t^{\beta+\gamma}}{\Gamma(\gamma + \beta + 1)} + \frac{t^{\gamma+\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha + \gamma + 1)},$$

$$z_3 = \frac{t^{2\gamma+\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 2\gamma + 1)} + \frac{2t^{\beta+\alpha+\gamma}}{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \gamma + 1)} + \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + 1)t^{\beta+\alpha+\gamma}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)\Gamma(\beta + 1)\Gamma(\alpha + \beta + \gamma + 1)} + \frac{t^{2\gamma+\beta}}{\Gamma(\beta + 2\gamma + 1)},$$

etc. Hence, the HPM series solutions are be given by

$$\begin{cases} x(t) = x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots, \\ y(t) = y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3 + \dots, \\ z(t) = z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3 + \dots. \end{cases}$$

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